

Complexes of Silver Perchlorate with Substituted Pyridines

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Silver perchlorate was treated with different substituted pyridines and five diamagnetic, two-coordinated linear complexes having the general formula $[AgL_n]ClO_4$ where L-2-methyl, 3-methyl, 4-methyl, 4-vinyl and 2:6-dimethyl pyridine were isolated. The infra-red absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} .

Several two-coordinated linear silver(I) complexes like $[Ag(NH_3)_2]^+$, $[Ag(CN)_2]^-$ are known¹. It also forms complexes where the coordination number is apparently three^{2,3}. Some α -picoline complexes of the cyanides, thiocyanates and cyanates of copper, silver and gold were reported⁴ earlier by Chauhan and Sinha. In this communication, we report some complexes obtained by reacting silver perchlorate with ligands containing nitrogen donor atom. 2-methyl, 3-methyl, 4-methyl pyridine (i.e., α , β and γ picolines); 2,6-dimethyl pyridine (2:6 lutidine) and 4-vinyl pyridine have been used as ligands.

EXPERIMENTAL

The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal as AgCl after digesting with dilute nitric acid. Carbon and hydrogen could not be estimated; however the percentage of silver is quite diagnostic to establish the correct composition. The conductance measurements were carried out using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CLO102 and a dip type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made with solid specimens using Gouy method. The infra-red absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the compounds: Silver perchlorate was prepared by treating silver oxide with insufficient amount of perchloric acid. Concentrated solution of silver perchlorate was treated with an aliquot amount of the ligand. White crystalline compounds separated out almost immediately. They were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried in vacuo. All these compounds are fairly soluble in acetone and insoluble in water. The relevant analytical and conductance data are recorded in table I.

TABLE I

Analysis, M. P. and Conductance of Silver(I) complexes with substituted pyridines.

Compound	M.P. (°C)	% Silver Found	% Silver Rqrd.	Λ_m in acetone (mhos)
1. Bis-(α -picoline) silver (I) perchlorate	156	27.0	27.4	162
2. Bis-(β -picoline) silver (I) perchlorate	150	26.8	27.4	179
3. Bis-(γ -picoline) silver (I) perchlorate	190	26.6	27.4	145
4. Bis-(2:6 Lutidine) silver (I) perchlorate	243(d)	25.2	25.7	167
5. Bis-(4-vinyl pyridine) silver (I) perchlorate	180(d)	24.3	25.8	143

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3. Cass, R. C., Coates, G.E. and Hayter, R.G., *Chem. and Ind.*, 1954, 1485.
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The absorption bands in the infra-red region from 5000 to 650 cm^{-1} for all the complexes are reported in table II.

TABLE II

Infra-red absorption bands in Nujol mulls of Silver(I) complexes with substituted pyridines

α -Picoline		β -Picoline		γ -Picoline		2:6 Lutidine		4-Vinyl pyridine	
L	AgL_2ClO_4	L	AgL_2ClO_4	L	AgL_2ClO_4	L	AgL_2ClO_4	L	AgL_2ClO_4
742(w)	740(s)	725(s)	720(vs) 730(sh)	820(s)	820(vs)	790(s)	808(vs)	808(s)	820(s)
765(s)	765(sh) 785(vs)	808(s)	800(sh) 820(vs) 840(sh)	1018(w)	1042(w)	1105(w)	1100(vs) 1125(w)	852(vs)	858(vs)
1018(w)			840(sh) 945(w)		1100(br. st) (1080-1130)	1165(w)	1180(s)	950(s)	956(s)
1062(s)		1042(s)	1042(s)					1010(vs)	1005(s)
					1225(w)		1265(w)		
1160(s)	1120(br. st) (1080-1140) 1258(w)	1120(w)	1120(br. st) (1100-1140)		1245(w)	1380(w)	1420(w)	1081(w)	
		1138(w)	1600(s)	1620(s)	1460(br)				1100(br. st) 1080-1120
		1200(s)	1210(s)			1580(s)	1590(vs)	1230(m)	1210(w)
1305(s)	1322(vs)		1250(m)			1590(s)	1612(vs)	1238(m)	1245(m)
		1420(s)						1422(vs)	1422(s)
1490(s)		1485(s)							1440(s)
1578(w)	1580(s)	1580(s)	1585(s) 1605(vs)					1508(s)	1505(s)
1600(s)	1610(vs)							1558(s) 1600(vs)	1550(s) 1612(vs)

s- sharp, m-medium, w-weak, vs-very sharp, sh-shoulder, br. st-broad and strong, L-ligand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Univalent silver ion has a symmetrical completely filled d^{10} non-bonding shell and causes least perturbation to any preferred stereochemistry of the complex. A linear two covalent complex can be regarded as arising from the use of sp hybrid bonds and a tetrahedral four covalent complex can be formed involving the use of sp^3 hybrid orbitals for bonding. Several compounds belonging to each category have been reported in the literature. Bis-quinoline (isoquinoline) silver (I) perchlorate was shown earlier⁵ to be a two coordinated ionic complex.

The perchlorate complexes reported now have the composition AgL_2ClO_4 (L = Ligand). The molar conductance values in acetone medium for 1:1 electrolytes lie in the range 150–200 mhos and the $\Delta\mu$ values now obtained for the complexes (table I) indicate them to be uni-univalent electrolytes. Hence, perchlorate remains outside the coordination sphere as an anion. Recently, it was shown⁶ that perchlorate can also coordinate to the metal. In the compounds under report, the ionic nature of the perchlorate has been definitely

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indicated by the electrolytic behaviour of the complex. In the infra-red region, the ionic perchlorate absorbs⁷ in the range 1050–1170 cm^{-1} and the broad absorption bands noticed in all the complexes in this region (Table II) lend further proof for the ionic nature of the perchlorate group. The absorption spectra of the free ligands are also given for comparison in table II along with those of the complexes. In all cases, some of the absorption bands of the free ligand are split and/or shifted to higher frequencies on being bonded to the metal which is to be expected in case of coordination complexes, since the ligand is not free. Some ligand absorption bands round about 1400 and 1500 cm^{-1} were masked in the complexes due to heavy absorption in this region by Nujol. The direct metal-nitrogen stretching frequencies could not be recorded since they are beyond the range of the instrument. The perchlorate complexes with the substituted pyridines reported now are therefore few more examples of the more usual two-coordinated linear complexes of silver (I).

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